

Application of a Cluster Analysis to Pollutant Factors in a Shallow, Eutrophic Lake

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Assuming that the pollution of a shallow lake in a plain is caused by two apparently different processes; the one involves the movement of pollutants directly flowing into the lake from the catchment area (allochthonous type or external cause type) and the other involves accumulation of substances mainly produced in the lake (autochthonous type or internal cause type). The attempt to prove the assumption was made using 20 factors bottom sediment and a statistical analysis as a case example in lake Inba-numa, Japan. A cluster analysis of the similarities of the station upon 20 factors and 3 combined factors types that is considered to be allochthonous; autochthonous and both types gave the result of eight areas and five groups in the lake, respectively. It was considered that both allochthonous and autochthonous types occurred nearly simultaneously, and the lake had been polluted by combined type.

Ecological nature of the lake and the pond in plains which had close relationship with our living activities from olden time through irrigation, fishing, transportation and recreation, has changed remarkably since the 1960s. The change could be appraised by accumulation of sludge in lakes and inflows of a large amount of domestic and/or industrial waste water through basin rivers¹⁻³.

In particular, the pollution of a closed water system has considerably aggravated, accelerating the progress of eutrophication. The research of the environmental dynamics in lakes and ponds and their catchment areas, has shifted from that dealing with increasing productivity to that of new ecological systems. As the oligotrophic lake had increasingly enhanced their value, it has become necessary to take measures to reduce the speed of the progress of utrophication. Efforts to determine the mechanism of eutrophication from the present condition of the ecological system in lakes and their catchment areas have been made in detail mainly of lake Biwa⁴, Kasumigaura⁵ and Suwa⁶ in Japan.

The lake, Inba-numa (surface area, 11.55 sq km; mean depth, 1.7 m; maximum depth, 3.0 m) in Chiba Prefecture is situated about 20 km from Tokyo. The lake consists of two major open waters : the western and northern basins connected with a canal. This study was carried out regarding the western part of lake Inba-numa which was strongly affected by human activities. In the present study, the pollution of the shallow western part of lake Inba-numa was largely classified into processes of pollution through movement of pollutants directly flowing into the lake from the catchment areas via rivers and that through accumulation of substances produced by metabolic production in the lake. A cluster analysis was made with several assumptions. It was tested whether these assumptions would be significant from the results of measurements. A statistical method was effective for examination, with emphasis on the accumulation of upper layer in the lake sediment.

Results and Discussion

Bottom materials : Table 1 shows the results

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of analysis of 20 factors of the bottom materials at 62 stations. The results varied from factor to factor and from station to station. The stations giving the maximum values were located at the place where the pollutants directly flowed in the lake from the outside and/or where load substances are present, secondarily produced upon these pollutants in the lake with well developed aquatic macrophytes.

Grouping by a cluster analysis : Through cluster analysis (median method) of the similarities of the station upon the 20 factors as well as the observations at the field measurement, the said 62 stations were clustered, as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The scale

Fig 1 Results of the cluster analysis on physicochemical characteristics

represents the degree of similarity between the stations based on Euclidean square distance.

The probability of the similarity among stations in the group was high.

By cluster analysis, the stations were classified into 8 groups of A through H. Judging from the available environmental data of measurement (pH, COD, SS, T-N, T-P and metals) and general information obtained from the field surveys, inflow from rivers, condition of the lake bottom by exploration, situation of aquatic macrophytes vegetation, movement of water, execution of dredging, etc., the following grouping of the lake was done. Group A : Collective and initial dispersion open water with inflow of rivers of Shin and Kashima. Group B : Joint area where the water of western part of lake Inba-numa mixes with the water coming from the northern main lake Inba-numa. Group C : Water area where the water containing mainly residual fertilizers from paddy fields might inflow and disperse and macrophyte vegetation fringes. Group D : Open water serving as the main course of fishing boats. Group E : The place intaking the service water, industrial water and supply water. Group F : The place where the bottom sediment was dredged in 1963 (dredged to 3 m at the deepest location). Group G : Water area where mainly the water from the canal joins into the water of Shin and Kashima rivers. Group H : Water area where aquatic vegetation of *Trapa* is developing.

Grouping by external and internal causations : The investigated 20 factors were specifically selected, based on the following considerations. Generally, it is considered that pollutants in a lake should be classified into three types. The first one is allochthonous⁷ one or pollutants coming from external origin (the pollution is caused by inflow of domestic and/or industrial waste water due to human activities within the catchment area of the lake). As the factors which relate to this external type, the following were considered: pH, T-N, NH₄-N, T-P, PO₄-P, MBAS (methylene blue active substance), zinc and lead. The second type is autochthonous^{7,8} one or pollutants caused by the lake itself. (The pollution

Fig 2 Eight parts (A through H) were marked out by the cluster analysis in the western part of lake Inba-nun

is attributed to microorganisms, metabolism of lake and autotrophic production by plankton, aquatic macrophytes, and substance derived by their food web. Eutrophication is accelerated by the increase of such organic pollutants). As factors relating to this internal type, the followings were taken : moisture content, ignition residue, organic carbon and phenophytin. The third type is mixed one of the above two types. As factors attributed to this type, all factors were considered. The relation of these types are graphically shown in Fig. 3.

As a result of cluster analysis point of view, the stations could be divided largely into 5 groups (Figs. 4 and 5). The probability of the similarity among stations in the group was high. Group 1 is considered to represent the water area where the zone of an emergent vegetation of *Zizania*, *Phragmites* and *Typha* growing at the rivermouth of the river Shin serves to reduce the pollution inflowing through the river and/or where the mass transfer seems to occur from the bottom mud into water by the absorption of the floating plant, *Trapa*⁹. In this group, the respective factors shows lower value than the mean value, except moisture content, nickel and manganese. Group 2 represents a water area where the influx of pollutants through the

Type I; allochthonous, or external causation.
Type II; autochthonous, or internal causation.
Type III; attributable to both types.

Fig 3 Schematic diagram of grouping of pollutants

river Kashima spread continuously into the center of lake. Accordingly, the contribution of external pollutants is significant. Group 3 represents a water area where surface flow due to prevailing wind is predominant. Group 4 represents a water area where pollutants through the river Kashima are greatly spread into the open water. Group 5 represents the area where the water of cut-off canal joins and mixes with the water from two rivers of Shin and Kashima.

According to the analytical values of the bottom

Fig. 4. Results of cluster analysis using the external type, the internal type and the combined type.

materials of these groups (Table 1), it is observed that the pollution tended to decrease in the order : Group 5 > Group 4 > Group 3 > Group 2 > Group 1.

Combined pollution caused by both external and internal types of pollutants : The external type and the internal type of pollution are separately shown in Fig. 6, which were obtained by cluster

analysis and also the results of field survey were overlapped. It was previously thought that the external and internal types of pollutants would present different aspects of classification, but the reality showed nearly similar aspect except for artificial dredge area in 1963. It is, therefore, estimated that while the individual factors of investigation may vary from station to station, the external and internal factors generally combined simultaneously in the lake. A great influence of pollutants from the rivers Shin and Kashima (Table 1), having aquatic plant vegetation remarkably developed and being greatly affected by surface flow due to prevailing wind, was elucidated.

Conclusion : The lake Inba-numa has been exposed to a serious eutrophic state by allochthonous pollutants attributed to human activities. Water area can be grouped with the cluster analysis using 20 factors. As a result, the western part of lake Inba-numa was divided into 8 water areas. However according to the consideration of the pollution coming from external origin or internal origin, the stations were divided into 5 groups.

More detailed studies on limnological, environmental, sanitary and agrochemical point of view are needed.

Experimental

Previous analytical data obtained in a field survey, including the water quality of the lake and of its catchment areas, aquatic vegetation, location of river-mouths and source of water supply, were used as a main source informations¹⁰. The 62 characteristic stations in the western part of lake Inba-numa were chosen for the bottom survey. The bottom materials were collected in the form of nearly complete columnar cores with a specially designed sampler from May 1984 to 1986. The bottom samples taken from the upper surface to a depth of 3 cm were immediately offered for chemical analysis. 20 factors (Table 1) were chosen for the analysis. After pretreatment according to the conventional method^{11,12}, copper, zinc, lead, nickel and manganese were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (using an Hitachi 180-30 spectrometer), chromium and arsenic by absorption spectrophotometry (using a Shimadzu

Fig. 5. Five water areas divided by the cluster analysis using three types causations.

Fig. 6. Hydro-climatic area in the lake.

TABLE -- I TWENTY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE UPPER LAYER SEDIMENT IN LAKE INBA-NUMA.

Station no.	pH	Moisture %	Ig-loss %	Org-C %	mgkg ⁻¹		T-N	NH ₄ -N	mg/dm ⁻³		PO ₄ -P	Pheo-phytin	MBAS	mgkg ⁻¹										Fe dry%
					T-P	NH ₃ -N			Cd	Cu				Zn	Pb	Ni	Cr	As	Mn	T-Hg				
Group 1 :																								
1	7.3	20.2	2.1	0.32	1.27	0.04	0.35	0.06	32.7	3.2	0.90	15.0	32.1	23.0	17.5	13.0	2.6	336	0.05	1.80				
2	7.3	64.7	15.6	2.98	2.77	0.07	0.49	0.04	69.8	5.6	1.10	45.4	52.4	29.3	35.6	24.4	7.4	1280	0.1	2.97				
3	7.2	65.9	15.0	4.69	6.51	0.09	0.50	0.09	85.1	5.0	1.24	65.0	64.6	29.3	35.4	28.5	5.4	1450	0.18	3.83				
4	7.2	45.3	8.1	2.25	2.40	0.06	0.34	0.04	55.3	6.0	0.97	30.0	50.3	20.9	35.3	28.7	2.2	807	0.09	3.59				
5	7.4	26.8	3.3	0.35	0.38	0.03	0.18	0.06	11.6	3.2	0.28	7.5	7.6	6.3	10.0	7.3	1.0	202	0.03	0.98				
6	7.2	69.4	17.2	6.46	7.39	0.18	0.57	0.05	125.1	6.0	1.52	55.0	60.1	29.3	45.9	32.0	5.7	2240	0.11	4.69				
7	7.3	67.0	18.1	6.33	7.54	0.10	0.63	0.12	116.4	6.4	1.52	55.2	64.3	25.1	40.5	34.7	1.7	1970	0.12	4.84				
8	7.1	71.8	20.4	5.30	7.35	0.07	0.51	0.07	87.3	5.0	1.52	50.0	44.7	25.1	35.4	28.2	3.0	1450	0.22	4.53				
9	7.5	23.7	1.8	0.26	0.24	0.02	0.12	0.07	7.3	3.0	1.38	7.5	7.9	8.4	15.8	11.4	1.4	269	0.02	2.11				
10	7.3	59.8	14.2	2.71	1.96	0.05	0.32	0.06	42.2	5.2	1.24	25.0	32.4	16.7	35.0	22.6	3.6	824	0.01	2.94				
46	7.2	35.7	8.6	1.64	2.04	0.16	0.68	0.02	40.0	16.4	1.24	35.0	70.0	37.7	35.8	28.5	1.1	549	0.13	3.31				
48	7.5	23.4	4.0	0.85	0.44	0.06	0.27	0.01	5.0	38.8	0.41	17.5	26.2	12.2	22.5	19.7	2.3	283	0.03	1.65				
50	7.7	33.1	5.9	1.52	0.99	0.09	0.47	0.07	29.1	14.5	0.97	35.0	50.3	25.1	30.0	26.4	1.7	531	0.04	2.88				
51	7.0	50.5	13.6	5.82	5.25	0.16	0.81	0.07	25.5	16.5	1.24	40.0	70.4	8.4	25.0	30.3	1.2	956	0.08	2.70				
56	7.4	58.2	23.4	8.59	7.15	0.15	1.35	0.04	52.9	14.5	1.67	35.6	50.9	20.9	40.4	24.2	1.0	624	0.17	3.87				
57	7.4	29.9	5.6	2.00	2.42	0.12	0.69	0.13	36.4	10.4	1.10	25.9	40.3	16.7	20.1	24.0	2.3	239	0.10	2.61				
58	7.1	42.9	13.5	4.02	3.92	0.09	1.30	0.10	5.0	10.0	1.52	40.0	52.2	20.9	35.6	34.3	3.6	661	0.13	4.95				
59	7.1	34.2	8.5	2.44	2.36	0.07	0.75	0.13	5.0	9.6	1.24	35.5	32.0	16.7	25.3	26.2	4.0	495	0.07	3.51				
60	7.2	29.4	6.8	2.14	1.94	0.07	0.46	0.02	7.3	10.0	1.24	35.0	30.4	37.7	25.0	24.1	3.0	440	0.03	2.67				
X	7.3	44.8	10.8	3.19	3.39	0.09	0.57	0.07	44.2	10.0	1.17	34.5	44.2	21.6	29.8	24.7	2.9	821	0.10	3.18				
Group 2 :																								
11	7.0	66.3	19.2	6.73	7.84	0.25	1.02	0.04	181.1	14.8	1.67	55.2	112.4	35.5	40.0	36.1	2.4	1350	0.15	4.22				
12	7.2	69.7	20.1	7.06	8.97	0.13	0.81	0.09	174.5	10.2	1.24	40.1	104.0	25.1	30.4	28.4	1.0	1400	0.18	6.86				
13	7.0	65.3	17.2	6.79	7.44	0.22	0.61	0.06	122.2	9.0	1.52	55.4	110.3	33.5	45.3	42.0	2.8	1600	0.12	4.84				
14	7.0	61.4	18.5	10.23	8.57	0.30	0.80	0.06	134.5	16.2	1.79	55.3	160.2	33.5	45.0	58.2	9.4	1040	0.06	5.00				
18	6.3	58.9	16.1	5.79	5.68	0.28	1.22	0.07	238.5	14.8	1.93	55.1	94.6	25.1	45.2	36.1	9.7	924	0.08	4.38				
19	7.3	67.3	18.2	6.33	6.47	0.32	1.77	0.06	203.6	12.8	1.67	55.0	130.1	29.3	45.5	38.0	1.5	1090	0.15	4.61				
20	7.0	50.3	12.2	7.27	7.43	0.25	1.96	0.07	269.1	16.4	1.67	55.2	130.4	25.1	45.0	36.4	4.2	992	0.11	4.22				
22	7.2	28.2	20.5	6.24	6.53	0.35	2.51	0.23	221.1	26.0	1.79	50.4	180.3	29.3	45.0	32.9	3.6	907	0.19	4.30				
23	6.9	65.0	21.2	6.27	6.24	0.16	1.86	0.29	229.1	19.2	0.97	50.5	130.8	25.1	40.1	30.3	4.0	922	0.23	3.64				
32	7.0	56.0	13.7	2.52	3.33	0.31	2.71	0.09	334.5	37.0	2.07	40.6	172.2	33.5	40.2	28.4	4.3	815	0.19	4.20				
47	7.0	39.7	8.7	3.68	3.76	0.16	0.87	0.11	72.7	21.6	1.67	55.0	110.2	46.0	40.4	40.6	4.0	584	0.59	3.39				
49	7.1	46.8	12.2	4.78	4.57	0.25	0.85	0.06	156.4	44.0	2.07	55.1	140.1	79.5	45.0	46.2	2.6	602	0.14	3.31				
53	7.3	27.3	4.4	0.80	0.86	0.06	0.86	0.20	5.0	10.0	0.90	17.5	120.4	10.5	37.5	22.0	1.0	239	0.05	2.22				
54	7.0	31.5	7.0	1.58	2.02	0.10	0.73	0.05	14.5	15.6	1.67	30.6	110.6	16.7	50.1	26.3	1.0	294	0.08	2.67				
55	6.9	28.4	6.3	1.86	2.22	0.07	0.54	0.02	7.3	11.0	1.79	40.0	112.5	16.7	25.3	22.0	2.8	349	0.05	2.61				
X	7.0	50.8	14.4	5.20	5.46	0.21	1.27	0.10	157.6	18.6	1.63	47.4	128.0	31.0	41.3	34.9	3.6	874	0.16	4.02				
n = 15																								

Table 1 (Contd.)

Group 3 :																				
15	7.2	72.1	20.5	6.99	7.74	0.40	1.75	0.03	289.5	16.8	3.31	99.8	119.0	96.2	60.0	96.5	5.7	790	0.15	4.61
24	6.9	77.0	24.9	9.14	9.97	1.11	5.21	0.20	429.1	96.1	2.62	85.0	989.7	58.6	50.0	42.2	3.0	1040	0.49	4.39
26	6.9	69.9	23.1	8.83	7.99	1.40	5.98	0.13	421.8	45.1	3.03	95.8	870.0	50.2	45.2	40.3	1.0	1090	0.72	4.30
30	6.8	74.1	23.9	10.22	9.95	2.00	4.16	0.43	429.1	88.0	2.76	99.8	830.7	58.6	52.8	44.8	1.3	1075	0.52	4.67
31	6.8	59.5	21.7	7.66	9.90	0.76	4.74	0.27	363.6	89.7	3.17	95.2	860.0	62.8	43.7	44.3	1.2	1060	0.64	4.95
34	6.6	64.8	23.7	9.45	9.38	0.49	4.55	0.57	71.3	95.6	2.62	98.5	926.8	62.8	45.0	48.5	3.1	574	0.86	3.70
37	7.0	69.4	26.9	7.99	9.80	0.63	3.53	0.30	77.8	87.9	2.34	85.0	934.5	62.8	55.7	46.0	4.0	481	1.05	3.70
42	7.0	64.6	21.7	9.21	9.58	0.91	4.43	0.02	225.5	86.0	3.31	97.1	971.0	99.9	70.0	92.4	6.3	867	0.83	4.66
$\bar{X}$	6.9	68.9	23.3	8.69	9.29	0.96	4.29	0.24	288.5	75.7	2.90	94.5	812.7	69.0	52.8	56.9	3.2	872	0.66	4.37
n = 8																				
Group 4 :																				
16	7.1	70.8	20.0	69.7	8.06	0.37	1.81	0.03	270.5	18.8	2.34	65.0	390	46.0	60.0	82.5	1.3	1090	0.16	4.69
17	7.0	71.3	21.3	7.76	7.68	0.32	1.43	0.03	194.9	29.4	2.34	70.0	248	41.8	60.0	66.2	2.1	1060	0.13	4.53
21	6.7	71.9	23.8	8.10	8.61	0.34	3.02	0.17	257.5	35.2	1.93	65.0	248	25.1	40.0	36.9	4.4	870	0.28	4.58
28	6.9	62.2	18.3	6.07	7.92	0.61	3.91	0.05	149.1	76.0	1.79	60.0	420	46.0	40.0	38.2	4.0	815	0.29	4.49
33	6.8	55.1	12.7	4.83	5.45	0.45	2.15	0.04	334.5	59.0	1.38	55.0	234	29.3	40.0	34.0	5.2	833	0.21	4.02
36	7.1	32.9	8.0	1.71	2.67	0.23	1.16	0.23	10.9	39.0	0.83	35.0	230	25.1	35.0	22.1	1.5	204	0.17	2.75
38	7.2	34.7	7.0	1.44	1.51	0.27	1.08	0.17	5.0	54.0	1.10	35.6	234	25.1	30.0	22.6	2.3	185	0.19	2.56
39	7.3	34.3	8.3	1.69	2.20	0.26	1.19	0.13	10.9	16.8	2.21	75.8	248	25.1	30.0	24.3	1.0	222	0.20	2.94
41	7.3	60.0	19.4	9.17	11.19	1.03	3.78	0.04	258.2	73.6	2.34	75.2	370	46.0	80.0	76.8	1.0	1100	0.66	4.75
43	6.9	43.5	10.1	1.10	4.67	0.32	2.49	0.04	176.0	12.0	2.48	105.9	250	87.9	100.0	99.7	9.7	673	0.17	3.95
44	7.0	48.0	13.4	5.45	4.89	0.29	2.24	0.03	78.5	54.8	1.93	98.5	290	155.0	95.0	98.9	7.7	637	0.22	3.98
45	6.6	49.0	12.9	6.33	5.15	0.30	2.69	0.13	78.5	52.0	1.38	25.0	260	138.0	65.0	89.9	7.7	726	0.18	3.90
52	7.3	29.8	6.9	1.69	1.88	0.09	1.07	0.06	10.2	16.4	1.52	65.2	120	29.3	75.0	48.7	1.4	312	0.08	2.70
61	7.1	38.8	9.5	5.85	6.47	0.27	1.59	0.48	32.0	130.0	1.67	55.8	380	46.0	30.0	32.6	2.8	275	0.26	2.88
62	7.1	56.0	17.3	4.14	5.50	0.27	1.78	0.24	46.5	126.0	1.79	30.0	350	33.5	30.0	24.7	2.6	239	0.65	2.43
$\bar{X}$	7.0	50.6	13.9	4.82	5.59	0.36	2.09	0.12	127.5	52.9	1.80	61.1	285	53.3	54.0	53.2	3.6	616	0.26	3.68
n = 15																				
Group 5 :																				
25	6.9	71.3	23.1	5.82	9.01	0.77	4.44	0.16	272.7	102.0	2.48	65.4	590	33.5	40.0	32.9	1.0	889	0.59	3.27
27	6.9	67.1	20.1	5.71	9.12	0.73	3.71	0.08	258.2	70.0	2.34	75.6	670	46.0	40.0	38.1	1.2	759	0.36	4.21
29	6.9	64.0	17.5	7.14	7.25	0.66	4.86	0.06	385.5	91.0	2.34	75.6	730	50.2	40.0	42.7	3.0	1040	0.39	4.86
35	7.1	71.1	27.9	9.59	14.06	1.27	5.06	0.25	43.6	385.0	3.45	110.0	1550	62.8	45.0	42.2	3.1	500	1.64	3.89
40	7.0	65.0	27.1	6.94	9.54	0.75	3.26	0.15	60.4	122.5	1.93	80.0	580	62.8	35.0	36.3	1.0	395	1.06	3.04
$\bar{X}$	7.0	67.7	23.1	7.04	9.81	0.84	4.27	0.14	204.1	154.1	2.51	81.3	824	51.1	40.0	38.4	1.9	717	0.81	3.93
n = 5																				

Bold figures and $\bar{X}$ show the maximum or minimum values and the mean values in each group (see the text concerning to five groups (Group 1 through 5)), (18-times analysed at each element).

UV-200A spectrophotometer), and total mercury was determined by gas chromatography (using a Shimadzu GC-5A instrument). pH was measured by the electrode method, moisture content and ignition residue by the gravimetric method, TOC by the titration method and TOC meter (using a Shimadzu 500 TOC meter) and nitrogen and phosphorus by absorption spectrophotometry. Analytical data of seasonal variations on bottom sediment may be neglected, because the core samples themselves are the accumulating production integrated with time in the lake.

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